

THE NAOS OF THE DECADES RECONSTITUTED

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ABSTRACT

In 1999, underwater excavation by the European Institute of Underwater Archæology (IEASM), in the Bay of Abukir, brought to light new fragments of a naos known since the early 19th century as *The Louvre Calendar*. It was later called *The Naos of the Decades* because of the very particular decoration of its outside surfaces which were separated into frames, one for each group of ten days of the ancient Egyptian year. This new discovery was the third one in the series of archæological episodes which allowed in the course of over two centuries to nearly complete the reconstitution of the monument: the roof of this naos was found in 1777 on land and belongs to the Louvre Museum; the base and the rear wall were found in 1940 under water in the Bay of Abukir, and our newly found items complete the major part of the lateral surfaces. Despite their stay of over one thousand years in salty water, the inscriptions preserved fairly well on the new items contradict the previously assumed distribution of the decades on the walls, and above all, shed an entirely new light on the interpretation of this important monument.

I. INTRODUCTION

The IEASM was created in 1985. I conceived it¹ with the object of bringing together Archæologists, Divers specializing in Archæology, scientific Engineers, especially in Geophysics, Archive Researchers, and also Curators and Restorers. The Institute works with state-of-the-art equipment and techniques, like e.g.: nuclear resonance magnetometres, and underwater differential GPSs which allow recording geographical positions below the surface of the sea. We systematically establish precise charts before beginning to excavate, and fine geophysical survey is associated with geological core sampling to determine the antique topography of submerged regions. These different data allow «surgical» digging, i.e.: targeted to predetermined points. The minutely precise positioning of cartographic details as well as of single objects offers not only great archæological interest, but also signals the significant advantage of perennial locating in the future. Use of these methods in the China Sea resulted in numerous successful missions, performed in collaboration with the National Museum of the Philippines, bringing to light shipwrecks of local junks of the Nanhai trade, Spanish galleons and East India Company vessels and the archæological treasures they had carried.

In 1992, I proposed to use these techniques in order to establish the cartography of the vestiges submerged in Alexandria at both the *Portus Magnus* and in the Bay of Abukir². The campaigns undertaken between 1996 and 2006 resulted in the discovery of two submerged cities, in still ongoing detailed topography of the region³, and also in the excavation of over 8000 artefacts, some of which have toured several continents in exhibitions⁴. Many were of a major historical interest, like e.g.: Nectanebo I's decree or the colossal stele of Ptolemy VIII; others

¹ See GODDIO, 2003A: 38-42; GODDIO, 2003B: 9-12.

² See GODDIO, 1995.

³ See GODDIO, 2007.

⁴ See GODDIO, 2008; GODDIO & FABRE, 2008.

were absolutely spectacular, like e.g.: the new fragments of the Naos of the Decades, which are going to be examined in this paper.

II. THE SURVEY AREA IN ABUKIR BAY

The survey area is vast: 110 km² [FIG. 1]. In historical times, immense land surfaces had vanished under the sea in the western part of Abukir Bay. This submergence may have been due to the conjunction of several phenomena including the rise of the sea level since Antiquity, and also natural catastrophic events. Geophysical and geological observations carried out by our missions with the cooperation of Professor Dr J.D. Stanley of the Smithsonian Institution⁵ and Profes-

sor Dr A. Nur of Stanford University, reveal evidence of landslides and geological collapse within this part of Abukir Bay and seismic after-effects in the clay sediment. Geological analysis found characteristic marks of soil liquefaction, i.e.: expulsion by compression of the water in the clay structures, abruptly reducing their volume and creating sudden subsidence⁶. The enormous weight of an abundant flood, or an earthquake, isolated or followed by a tsunami, can be the origin of such phenomena. The region is particularly subject to earthquakes⁷, and it is very likely that the succession of several such catastrophic events spread over time finally resulted in the very disappearance of this vast surface under the sea. The most recent artefacts found in the submerged area date from the 8th century AD⁸, which would place the definite submersion of a major part of the land in that period.

Two cities were discovered on this site: East Canopus and, slightly more than 3 km further east, the city of Heracleion on the very entrance into the Canopic Mouth [FIG. 2]. The spelling of *Heracleion* with a «c» instead of a «k» was decided when this town was discovered in order to differentiate it from the town of Hērakleion on the Island of Crete⁹. The fragments of the Naos of the Decades were found in the area of East Canopus.

III. THE DISCOVERY OF FOUR FRAGMENTS OF THE NAOS OF THE DECADES

The site of East Canopus is located at some 1.8 km off the coast of the modern port of Abukir [FIG. 2]. On the western side, remnants of buildings and numerous artefacts, especially the im-

⁵ See STANLEY *et al.*, 2001; STANLEY *et al.*, 2004.

⁶ See GODDIO, 2007: 8.

⁷ See NUR, 2010: 127 & fig. 10.1.

⁸ See GODDIO, 2007: 127; BRESC, 2008: 200-01, 304-05.

⁹ See COLE, 2007: XV.

FIGURE 2: The now submerged region of East Canopus and Heracleion–Thonis in a map designed by Franck Goddio. [From GODDIO, 2007: 25, fig. 1.24; © Franck Goddio & Hilti Foundation].

posing remains of the site designated as **TW4** reveal the biggest Egyptian sanctuary so far discovered on land or under the sea in the neighbourhood of Aboukir town [FIG. 3]. The hypothesis that it corresponds to the Serapeum of Canopus is supported by various arguments, especially its distance from the temple of Heracleion as mentioned in ancient texts, particularly Strabōn¹⁰, and above all, the statuary including the huge head which must have belonged to a colossal statue of Serapis dating from the 2nd century BC¹¹, as well as the presence of Byzantine remains which could correspond to the Methanoia Monastery built on that spot after the destruction of the Serapis sanctuary in 381 AD. In the eastern part (site **T**), four fragments of the naos were found relatively close together, probably near the location where Prince Tousoun discovered the base and the rear wall of this monument in 1940¹² [FIG. 4]. The black granite fragments of the naos were heavily encrusted with maritime growth, covered by not less than 50 cm of sediment.

FIGURE 3: The various sites of East Canopus in a map designed by Franck Goddio. [© Franck Goddio & Hilti Foundation].

¹⁰ See STRABŌN, *Geography*, Book 17.1: 17 (translation in YOYOTTE *et al.*, 1987: 109).

¹¹ See GODDIO, 2007: 67; KISS, 2008: 174-77.

¹² See HABACHI & HABACHI, 1952: 251.

FIGURE 4: Detail of the map of site T where the fragments of the naos were found. The four fragments of the Naos of the Decades are indicated by their excavation numbers (T1-)1244, 1245, 1246 and 1318. [Map designed by Franck Goddio; © Franck Goddio & Hilti Foundation].

IV. THE RECONSTRUCTION OF THE PUZZLE

IV.1. THE ROOF: It can be asserted at the first glance that the roof of the naos (Louvre D37) had never been submerged: it shows none of the characteristic traces immediately visible to the eye of an underwater Archæologist, like the small concretions of maritime fauna. The roof was thought to come from Damietta or Rosetta. Yoyotte¹³ established that in reality it had been found near Abukir, on 13 November 1777, when he understood that «la petite pyramide du plus beau marbre noir» mentioned in the recital of the explorer Sonnini de Manoncour was, in fact, the item in the Louvre. On that day, Sonnini had bought it from the man who had just found it at Abukir in front of his eyes. He could not remove it from Egypt, however, and left it in the French residency at Rosetta. The roof then appears in the collection of the Duc de Choiseuil-Gouffier, French Ambassador at Constantinople from 1784-1791, which collection entered into the Louvre Museum after his death in 1817.

IV.2. THE BASE AND REAR WALL: In 1933, Group Captain Cull commanding the RAF base at Abukir, noticed some visual abnormalities in the bay and informed Prince ‘Omar Toussoun, a great expert in Egyptian History in general, and that of Alexandria in particular¹⁴, a specialist on matters of the Delta and author of an *Exposé* on the ancient branches of the Nile¹⁵. The Prince immediately organized an exploration under water¹⁶, which — thanks to information from some fishermen — spotted some ruins in the vicinity (most probably on site T). He brought to light a lovely head of white marble, identified by Professor Breccia as the head of Alexander the Great. Just above human size, it lay in 5 m depth near some white marble and pink granite columns. This mission was followed by others in subsequent years, and in 1940, he discovered the base and rear wall of the naos. But it was only some time later that these two frag-

¹³ See YOYOTTE, 1954: 79-80.

¹⁴ See COMBE, 1943-44: 98-103.

¹⁵ See TOUSSOUN, 1922.

¹⁶ See TOUSSOUN, 1934: 342-54.

ments were connected with the monument in the Louvre. The Prince donated all the artefacts he found to the Helleno–Roman Museum of Alexandria, where the two contiguous parts of the naos were entered under number JE 25.774. In 1952, the Habachi brothers recognized that these and the roof in the Louvre belonged to the same structure, and immediately published the monument¹⁷.

FIGURE 5: The right wall of the Naos.
[Diagram: L. von Bomhard, IEASM].

FIGURE 6: The left wall of the Naos.
[Diagram: L. von Bomhard, IEASM].

IV.3. THE RIGHT LATERAL WALL: The artefact bearing the excavation number TI–1245, registered as SCA 162 by the Supreme Council of Antiquities, is the only fragment found that belongs to the right side of the naos, a large triangular piece fitting exactly into the remnants of the base and of the rear wall [FIG. 5]. Its outside shows all or part of Decades 14 to 21. Unfortunately, this side was turned up and exposed to sea water, friction and abrasion, thus the texts are severely damaged. The inside surface is less abraded and is divided into three horizontal registers decorated with divinities.

IV.4. THE LEFT LATERAL WALL: A very big fragment (TI–1244 / SCA 161) almost fills the upper part of the left wall. Another triangular part (TI–1246 / SCA 163) joins the preceding one, completing the lower forward part of that wall. A third small fragment (TI–1318 / SCA 164) further fills up part of the missing surface [FIG. 6]; contrary to the fragment from the right side, the two big parts of the left outside wall, are remarkably well preserved and the remaining texts are very largely readable. Decades 2, 3, 4 and 6 are practically complete, Decade 7 is partially preserved, and triangular fragment SCA 164 adds a small part of the astrological text of Decade 8. Most extraordinary is that the upper part of the biggest slab is not decorated with decade frames like all the others, but is covered with hieroglyphs in columns under decorative panels showing divinities. Luckily, a huge part of the text is preserved and readable, because it

¹⁷ See HABACHI & HABACHI, 1952: 251-63.

FIGURE 7: Cast of SCA 161.

[From GODDIO, 2003A: 56; © Franck Goddio & Hilti Foundation].

contains an original recital (without any parallel), explaining how the god Shū created the world, and how he set up the decanal stars. With the technique developed by the IEASM¹⁸, casts of all the texts could be established with a precision of one micron ($1\ \mu\text{m} = 10^{-3}$ of a millimetre). Due to the use of liquid silicone, this technique can even be used *in situ* under water. All the texts of the naos have been cast in this manner [FIG. 7].

FIGURE 8: The reconstituted Naos of the Decades.

[Photograph Ch. Gerigk; © Franck Goddio & Hilti Foundation].

V. CONCLUSIONS: THE NAOS OF THE DECADES RECONSTITUTED

The succession of exhibitions of thousands of artefacts discovered during the underwater excavations in the Great Eastern Port of Alexandria and in the Bay of Abukir provided the opportunity of assembling the various parts of the Naos of the Decades and showing it reconstituted. The history of this monument is highly unusual: it was ordered by Nectanebo I in the 4th century BC for the temple of a town in the East of the Delta, Saft 'el-Henna. Later — we ignore when— it was transported for unknown reasons to the Canopic region in the western part of the Delta. There, it was probably broken up during the famous destruction of the tem-

¹⁸ See BERNAND & GODDIO, 2002: 52-59; GODDIO, 2003A: 56-58.

ple of Canopus by the Christians¹⁹. Most of its fragments were found under water, on the site of East Canopus, close to the remnants of a temple compound, most probably the Serapeum of Canopus²⁰. Oddly enough, the roof had not been found under water, and it can be declared with absolute certainty that it has never been submerged. It was found close to the actual shore of Abukir, i.e.: some 1.8 km distant from the other fragments. Sonnini de Manoncour left it at Rosetta, and it ended in the Louvre some forty years later. Whereas the Naos of the Decades was dismembered and its various parts dispersed between the Louvre Museum, the Helleno–Roman Museum of Alexandria and the bottom of the Bay of Abukir, all these parts are now reassembled, to be studied and exhibited. Shown in exhibitions in various cities in Europe, Asia and North America²¹, it amazed and fascinated the general public as much as the Scholars by the highly unusual appearance of its decoration, the unique collection of texts it displays, and above all by the impressive aura of a «magical power» that it seems to radiate.

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¹⁹ See YOYOTTE, 1954: 80; GODDIO, 2007: 68.

²⁰ See GODDIO, 2007: 57.

²¹ Actually in Berlin (2006), Paris (2006), Bonn (2007), Madrid (2008), Turin (2009); Yokohama (2009); and the touring in USA: Philadelphia (2010), Cincinnati, Milwaukee (2011), Los Angeles (2012).